

BOLLYWOOD RISING: A CASE STUDY OF FDI IN HINDI FILM INDUSTRY

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Abstract

In 2002 Indian government allowed 100 percent FDI in Bollywood. Prior to that government had conceded the long-standing demand of the film producers and given the "industry" status to Bollywood, thus enabling it to borrow from banks and tapping stock markets. But, allowing 100 percent FDI in Bollywood proved to be a game changing decision. This paper undertakes the case study of the impact of allowing 100 percent FDI in the Bollywood and argues that it has made Indian film industry a force to reckon with. Film producers have started targeting entire world as their market. In the end, the proposed paper will make suggestions regarding how to attract more FDI in Indian film sector, which has the potential to make Bollywood even more competitive and productive.

Impact of Industry Status on Bollywood

Now let us return to our fundamental research question: what has been the impact of awarding industry status to Bollywood and allowance of 100 percent FDI. These decisions have proved to be game changers for Bollywood. Free and legal flow of capital in filmmaking has changed the face of Bollywood in last decade and half. Mergers and Acquisitions (M&A), which are the hallmark of a dynamic and growing economy, have become commonplace in film business. The seamless intermingling of domestic and global capital has made film production one of the most vibrant aspects of Indian economy. Rest of the paper undertakes the case study of how foreign capital has influenced the business of filmmaking in India¹.

After the government's decision to grant industry status to filmmaking in 1998, Bollywood's first priority was to use legitimate sources of financing only. By that time Mumbai police, alarmed by Gulshan Kumar's murder, had done a lot to bring Bollywood out of the shadow of underworld. For the first time, there was neither pressure nor need to take money from dubious sources.

It was possible for producers to approach banks and get white money for making films. Big production companies started tapping stock markets also. Consequently, many Indian companies became listed on stock exchanges. Filmmaking became like any other business: attracting investors, undertaking projects, completing them within strict time schedule, payment to actors and technical personals through checks, making profits and giving dividends to shareholders.

100 percent FDI and Bollywood

There was a gap of only four years (in 1998 and 2002) in the decision to accord industry status to Bollywood and to allow 100 percent FDI in filmmaking. Both these decisions were taken in the general milieu of economic liberalization program launched in 1991². Thus it is slightly difficult to understand which among these decisions led to what changes in Bollywood. But further discussion will clarify that changes initiated by economic liberalization and according industry status to Bollywood fructified in the game changing scenario only after the decision to allow 100 percent FDI in Bollywood.

Hollywood behemoth Viacom joined hands with Indian Production Company Network 18 to produce films in India. Subsequently, Reliance group of India bought Network 18's stake. The bevy of deals involving Viacom's India operations was an example of merger and acquisition activity in dynamic Indian film industry, which had become eligible for global and Indian private investment. The company ultimately emerged as Viacom 18 Motion Pictures (VMP), which became one of the most prominent producers of Hindi films.

Viacom produced films like *Queen* and *Mary Com* in 2014, which were critically acclaimed and also went on to become commercial success. In 2015, Viacom planned to release seven major films : *Gabbar is Back*, *Drishyam*, *Manjhi*, *Margarita with a Straw*, *Dharam in Sankat*, *Shimla Mirchi* and *Pyar Ka Panchnama 2*. Elaborating upon the different approach of Viacom, COO of company's Indian operation AjitAndhare said, "VMP's choice of films are centered around content that the new India wants to watch. This studio has consistently produced films that are shaping the new age Indian cinema whether it was *Kahaani* and *Gangs of Wasseypur* in the past or films like *Bhaag Milkha bhag*, *Madras Café*, *Queen* and *Mary Kom* recently.³ These films have found box office success and also emerged as winners in best film category across various awards. As a studio we are constantly looking to define and shape a new mainstream that does not see box office success and acclaim as two different goalposts but one seamless outcome, our films in 2014 demonstrated this and our slate for 2015 further builds on that approach.

Launched in 2008, Fox Star Studio itself is a joint venture between Hollywood major 20th Century Fox and Star Network, a company from Rupert

Murdoch's media conglomerate. According to an estimate, Fox Star Studio has captured 40 percent of Indian film production market. It has achieved a turnover of 8 to 10 billion rupees and figures in top three studios of India, rubbing shoulders with UTV Motion Pictures and Eros International . In 2014 Fox Star released a movie almost every two weeks. Fox Star copied its own movie Knight and Day (2010) and remade it in Hindi as Bang Bang.

Among American players, Sony Pictures Entertainment (SPE) is a lone Japanese company. SPE is a subsidiary of Sony Entertainment Inc, an arm of Tokyo based Sony Corporation. It owns Columbia Pictures and Tristar Pictures in Hollywood. Sony was the first foreign company to produce a film in India in 2007. Way back in 2004 Sony's distribution revenue in India crossed the Rs 100 crore mark . Initially Sony formed a joint venture with Indian promoters. But, in 2012, it bought Indian promoters' 32 percent stake in \$ 271 millions. According to its own website, "Sony Pictures India is the #1 Hollywood studio in India with 5 out of the top 10 Hollywood films of all time in India including blockbusters like 2012 (2009), The Amazing Spider-Man (2012), The Amazing Spider-Man 2 (2014), Spider-Man 3 (2007) and Skyfall (2012)⁴. SPE's global operations encompass motion picture production and distribution; television production and distribution; home entertainment acquisition and distribution; a global channel network; digital content creation and distribution; operation of studio facilities; development of new entertainment products, services and technologies; and distribution of entertainment in more than 159 countries."⁵

Another Hollywood major studio Warner Brothers established a subsidiary Warner Bros Pictures India to oversee production and distribution business. In 2003, company was cautious about its India plans. A spokesperson for the company said that Warner Bros would wait and watch before expanding its India horizons. Spokesperson added "We are still testing the waters here and a lot of legalities are to be cleared before we expand and bring other Bollywood films within our ambit⁶.

Interestingly, due to strong distribution network of Hollywood studios, Indian films have even been able to penetrate Chinese market. In May 2015, UTV joined hands with Chinese Distributer NERPG to release Bollywood super hit film PK in almost every Chinese city. In the first week itself, PK earned \$10 millions in the Chinese market. A Chinese analyst described the success of PK in China market as "game changing", because unlike UK, US and Canada market, there is no Indian diaspora in China. (Krishnan 2015). PK was released in 3,500 screens and another big hit Happy New Year (2014) hit 5,000 screens in China. These numbers would not have been possible without the strength of Hollywood's distribution and marketing network. Bollywood's Chinese invasion is significant because China is the second largest movie market after Hollywood.

It's not that just Hollywood studios are taking Bollywood films to global markets. Following the true spirit of globalization, Indian business houses are also eyeing movie-making business in the US. Indian businessman Anil Ambani has decided to invest around \$825 million as a first tranche towards making six films a year for global audiences. In one of the largest deals in global cinema in recent times, Ambani teamed up with noted Hollywood filmmaker Steven Spielberg for the Los Angeles-based production house, Dreamworks Studios.⁷

Coroporatization of filmmaking business, professionalism and availability of finance are the other changes ushered in by 100 percent FDI. Off course, these changes are part of globalization itself. And these changes also promote even more globalization⁸. Foreign consumers are increasingly patronizing its offerings, adding to the industry's already massive domestic audience.

As far as corporatization is concerned, Indian film companies - Eros, Adlabs, and India Film Company, have raised hundreds of millions of pounds from hungry institutional investors on the AIM facility of London Stock Exchange. Film producers are interested in creating serious corporate structures. Coropratization is changing the business model of Bollywood.

A necessary aspect of globalization in free movement of ideas, people and technology. There was a time when getting foreign exchange and permission to shoot abroad was a Herculean task. But with the liberalization of film industry, it has become norm to have a shooting schedule in foreign location. Many governments offer special incentives to Bollywood in order to boost their tourist economy. With the help of international studios, it has become much easier to take care of logistics problems in a foreign locale. Few examples of films which were shot abroad are: Dilwale Dulhania Le Jayenge, Rockstar, Kal Ho Na Ho, Jab Tak Hai Jaan, Ek Main Aur Ek Tu, Dostana, New York, Bachna Ai Haseenon, Zindagi Na Milegi Dobara⁹. This is part of a cross-over film phenomenon - films that work with audiences within and outside India, but appear to target the non-resident Indian.

Again the phenomenon has been possible because of close interaction of Hollywood studios and Bollywood film community. Apart from this, Hollywood movies such as Avengers, Mission Impossible: The Rogue Nation, Fast and Furious 6&7, The Jurassic World are released simultaneously in India with the global release. IBEF points out that viewership of Hollywood movies is on the rise in India. Hollywood production houses have increased their focus on the Indian market because of growing revenues from their releases in India.

Problems International Investors Face

It is only natural that international investors will face a few challenges while working in any country, at least initially. But some of the problems faced by global investors in Bollywood are such that they are hampering the free flow

of capital. Piracy and inability of Indian law enforcement agencies to curb it are the biggest problems faced by International Studios. An Indian producer said that piracy eats up to 60 percent of revenues of Indian film industry every year. The film industry was in fact significantly impacted by online piracy. In 2008, piracy cost the Indian film industry \$959 million and about 571,000 jobs. A study undertaken by the Motion Picture Distributors Association has put India among the top ten countries in the world where online piracy is highest. Research has shown that online piracy of film and TV network is mainly through file sharing networks. Drawing attention to the problems faced by international investors. Motion Picture Association of America (MPAA) chairman Dan Glickman said, "Free is great and everybody likes things for free. In a civilized society we need to pay for product and services. It's a very unusual situation for global money." If piracy is curbed, international money will flow more freely in Bollywood¹⁰.

Black money is another major problem faced by global investors. Bollywood has a history of almost 100 years of dealing with money laundering and black money. Several Bollywood big guns were caught on camera admitting the fact that money laundering is rampant in the film industry, in a sting operation conducted by Cobrapost & CNN IBN¹¹. The sting operators were seen persuading the filmmakers to let them invest money in film productions in a way that would help them convert black money into white. This is again a very bad situation for international studios.

Hollywood works on the basis of studio system but Bollywood has its own star system. A British newspaper remarks, while every other branch of cinema has seen the advent of new attitudes and approaches to work, the stars (and wannabes) are doing the same what their predecessors did 50 years ago and often more greedily. In no other film industry, do star salaries account for 50 to 70 per cent of the budget like they do in India. Unreasonable demands too have sent production costs soaring. All stars are bound by strict Completion Bonds and Insurance covenants, but unfortunately star tantrums remain a way of life¹². The other sad part is today's stars rarely work with industry bodies to solve industry problems (this despite the fact nearly all of them are producers themselves). This malaise requires a rethink.

Underworld's shadow still looms large on Bollywood and it makes international investors very nervous. Leading Bollywood producer Gulshan Kumar was shot dead in 1997 and another producer Rakesh Roshan was shot at in January 2000. In 2010, leading producer Sajid Nadiadwal was threatened by the underworld. In 2014, underworld made a threat to leading Indian actors Shahrukh Khan and Akshay Kumar. Producers Mahesh Bhatt, Ram Gopal Verma, Boney Kapoor and singer Sonu Nigam also received death threats.

Hollywood has no experience in dealing with this kind of insecurity. These laws and order issues are major deterrent for free flow of foreign capital¹³.

India is a secular country but Hindu and Muslim religious organization constantly oppose films, which they believe, show their religion in negative light. Harassing actors and producers and stone-pelting at theaters showing the films are recurrent strategy. Recently Dharam Sankat Mein (2015), Dozakh: In Search of Heaven (2015), PK (2014), Baby (2015), Oh My God (2012) and My Name is Khan (2010) suffered the ire of religious groups¹⁴. These religious groups enjoy political patronage at times and it is difficult to deal with them. Again, India has to deal in a stern manner with the groups, which utilize the strategy of opposing films for cheap publicity¹⁵.

Indian films have to deal with Censor Board for Film Certification also. Censor board often goes to extreme in the guise of its agenda of not promoting vulgarity and not hurting national and religious feelings and asks producers to cut the scenes from their films, which are very basic for the story line. In 2015, censor board came up with the list of 28 cuss words, which could not be used in films. Representatives from government, censor board and film community need to sit down and resolve these problems which scare domestic as well as international producers¹⁶.

For producing films, Hollywood has a business model, which is far more sensible than Bollywood. The highlight of this system is a tripartite agreement that a financier has with a completion services company and the producer. If the producer is not able to complete the film, the completion services company steps in as a guarantor and underwrites the risk of the financier and takes over the production of the film¹⁷. This kind of bonding deals are unlikely to happen in India as the producers don't allow their films to be taken over. In order to attract foreign investment, Bollywood need to invent some kind of formal business model, which is acceptable to international studios.

Conclusion

Findings of this paper are rather obvious. This research investigated the impact of 100 percent FDI on Bollywood cinema. FDI has resulted in globalization of Hindi cinema, corporatization of film industry, advent of transparent financing and a bit of professionalism in filmmaking. Yet, there are many problems such as black money, money laundering, influence of the underworld, problems from religious groups, arbitrary decisions by censor boards and lack of a healthy business model which plague the Bollywood. These are big problems but hardly insurmountable. Government, film community and investors need to develop a strategic vision for Bollywood so that the flow of global capital increases further in Hindi film industry. There is more work needed to be done by academics in

collaboration with film produces regarding the resolution of problems plaguing the Bollywood.

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